

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15011806

Treasury Single Account as Determinant of Nigerian Banks' Soundness and Asset Base

Emmanuel Sunday Okwunodu & Prof Augustine Okolie

Department of Accounting,
Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the extent to which the Treasury Single Account (TSA) affects the soundness and asset base of commercial banks in Nigeria from 2001 to 2022. The population of the study consisted of 25 commercial banks as of December 31, 2022. The study focused on two key variables: TSA implementation and commercial banks' performance. The independent variable, TSA implementation, was measured by federal government deposits, while the dependent variable, bank soundness and asset base, was assessed through the capital adequacy ratio and non-performing loan ratio. The ordinary least squares (OLS) estimation technique was used to test the research hypotheses. The findings revealed that TSA implementation has a positive effect on the capital adequacy ratio (coefficient = 0.435524, p-value = 0.0090 < 0.05, t-value = 2.947146 > 1.96), indicating a significant relationship. Conversely, TSA, as captured by federal government deposits (FGD), showed a negative yet significant effect on asset quality (coefficient = -0.460583, p-value = 0.0488 < 0.05, t-value = -2.122758 < -1.96). Consequently, it is imperative for Nigerian bank regulators to ensure that the current capital adequacy ratio is maintained. This study contributes to the body of knowledge regarding the implications of TSA implementation in the Nigerian banking industry.

Keywords: Treasury Single Account, Non-performing loan; capital adequacy ratio; asset base, commercial banks

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the Nigerian banking has experienced several reforms and policies, some of the recent reforms in banking sector include raising the minimum capitalization for banks, Phased withdrawal of public sector funds from banks, starting in July, 2004, consolidation of banking institutions through mergers and acquisitions amongst others. Until the introduction of Treasury Single Account (TSA), government Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDA's) operated a multiplicity of accounts in commercial banks. The MDA's use part of the funds they generated to fund their operations and remitted the residual to the federation account (Ewiwile, Sinebe, Mokobia, Agbogun, & Ighorje, 2024).

Furthermore, the implementation of TSA in 2015 arguably threatened the liquidity position and profitability of Nigerian banking sector when all MDAs were mandated to pay all government revenues, incomes and other receipts into a single account with the Central Bank of Nigeria. This therefore, made CBN to reduce banks' cash reserve ratio (CRR) from 31% to 25% in 2015 in order to aid commercial bank liquidity management.

In Nigeria, the pilot TSA scheme started in 2012 using a unified structure of accounting for 217 government MDAs, for accountability and transparency in public fund management, the full implementation took effect in 2015. Under the arrangement, Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) can collect

revenue on behalf of MDAs using Government transit accounts but they must remit such takings to CRA at the end of the transaction day. The essence of TSA is to curb maintenance of multiple bank accounts by MDAs so as to effectively monitor government revenue, receipts and expenditures as well as block leakages among the public sector entities (Yusuf, 2016). TSA also seeks to address the issue of keeping idle funds in the MDAs (Yusuf, 2016). The unutilized public sector funds in the MDAs' bank accounts were the ones principally used by deposit money banks (DMBs) to generate free profit. In addition, the new cash management reform has in the short run, robbed off the DMBs of the monthly opportunity of safekeeping federal allocations released to the Federal, States and Local Governments through Federation Account Allocation Committee (FAAC). Dearth of deposited FAAC funds in the MDAs' bank accounts is another ugly signal of the implementation of the TSA to the shareholders and other stakeholders in Nigerian banking sector.

Nevertheless, one of the most controversial issues that have faced accounting research lies on the relationship between TSA and soundness and asset quality base in Nigeria. A great challenge facing most parts of the world and, particularly, the developing countries like Nigeria is how to achieve efficient allocation of resources as well as stabilization of the business cycles. An important factor for efficient management and control of government's cash resources is a unified structure of government banking. Such unified banking arrangements should be designed to minimize the cost of government borrowing and maximize the opportunity cost of cash resources. This requires that cash received is available for carrying out government's expenditure programmes and making payments in a timely manner. Many emerging markets and low-income countries have fragmented systems for handling government receipts and payments. In these countries, the ministry of finance/treasury lacks a unified view and centralized control over government's cash resources. Consequently, this cash lies idle for extended periods in numerous bank accounts held by spending agencies while the government continues to borrow to execute its budget. It is based on these reasons that the current global revolution in government accounting became paramount following which Nigeria has initiated and implemented the TSA and other series of economic policies to assist in the better management of her economy.

Again, most of the studies based their works on the benefits and challenges of TSA. Again, this is borne out of the need to determine whether with the TSA implementation, the targeted commercial banks were well rated and also had high predictive power which the extant empirical studies conducted in the Nigerian context did not consider. In like manner, most of the extant studies did not provide a conceptual model which shows the direction of relationship between TSA implementation and commercial banks' soundness and asset quality base in Nigeria. Arising from these perceived gaps coupled with the mixed results, this study seeks to ascertain the effect of Treasury Single Account on Commercial Banks' soundness and asset quality base in Nigeria. Specifically, this study intends to:

- i. Examine the degree to which TSA implementation influence the capital adequacy ratio of quoted commercial banks in Nigeria; and
- ii. ascertain the degree to which TSA implementation influence the asset quality ratio of quoted commercial banks in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

TSA is one of the financial policies implemented by the Federal Government of Nigeria to consolidate revenue from all ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs) way of deposits into commercial banks into a single account at the Central Bank of Nigeria. The policy was introduced to reduce the proliferation of bank accounts operated by MDAs and also to promote transparency and accountability among all organs of the government.

Yusuf (2016) said that TSA is "the Federal Government independent revenue e-collection initiative that will automate revenue collections of ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs) directly into the Federal Government consolidated revenue fund (CRF) account at the CBN through the Remitta e-collection and other electronic payment channels". Kanu (2016) views TSA as one of the financial policies implemented by the federal government of Nigeria to integrate all revenues and treasuries from

all ministries, departments and agencies and extra ministerial departments in the country where all the collections are paid into money depositing banks trailed to a single account at the apex bank of the nation (CBN). Thus, the introduction of TSA was expected to reduce the multiplicity of bank accounts previously maintained by various MDAs, thus, ensuring transparency and accountability in all organs of the government. Sabo, Muhammad and Ka'oje (2019), TSA is a public accounting system under which all government revenue, receipts, and income are collected into one single account, usually maintained by the country's Central Bank and all payments done through this account as well (Adeolu, 2016).

Before the introduction to TSA, Nigeria had fragmented banking arrangement for revenue and payment transactions. These were more than 10,000 bank accounts in multiple banks which made it impossible to establish government consolidated cash position at any point in time. It led to pockets of idle cash balances held in MDA's account when government was out borrowing money. (Yusuf, 2016) added that "the maintenance of Treasury Single Account will help ensure proper cash management by eliminating idle funds usually left with different commercial banks and in a way enhance reconciliation of revenue collection and payment.

The introduction of TSA is in line with the presidential Order No. 55 (2011), which stipulated that the Bureau of Treasury (BTR) will institute a Treasury Single Account to receive and remit collections of internal revenue taxes/customs duties from Bureau of Internal Revenue/Bureau of Customs, authorized money depositing banks and also National Government Agencies from authorized government depository banks. The TSA will be maintained at the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) (Ofor, Omaliko & Okoli, 2017).

The Central Bank of Nigeria therefore created an account called the „Consolidated Account“ to receive all government revenue and effect payments. This account is referred to as the Treasury Single Account. In 2012 the Nigerian government ran a pilot scheme for a single account using 217 ministries, departments and agencies as a test case. The pilot scheme saved Nigeria about N500 billion in frivolous spending. The success of the pilot scheme motivated the government to fully implement TSA, leading to the directives to banks to implement the technology platform that will help accommodate the TSA scheme. The directives by President Mohammed Buhari that all government revenues should be remitted to a Treasury Single Account is in consonance with this program and in compliance with the provisions of the 1999 constitution (CBN, 2015). All Ministries, Departments and Agencies are expected to remit their revenue collections to this account through individual deposit money banks who act as collection agents. With this arrangement, the money deposit banks will continue to maintain revenue collection accounts for Ministries, Departments and Agencies but all monies collected by these banks will have to be remitted to the Consolidated Revenue Accounts with the CBN at the end of each banking day.

Ali and Puah (2018) stressed that, asset quality can be expressed using the total loans to total assets ratio. The author added that, asset quality is an aspect of bank management that entails the evaluation of a firm's assets to facilitate the measurement of the level and size of credit risk associated with its operation. It relates to the left-hand side of the bank balance sheet and focuses on the quality of loans, which provide earnings for a bank. Asset quality and loan quality are two terms with basically the same meaning, while their management is considered important by the banking sector.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

The Diffusion of Innovations (DOI) Theory was used to underpin the study. This theory seeks to explain how, why, and at what rate new ideas and technology spread through cultures (Yusuf, 2016). Rogers (1995) explained diffusion as the process by which an innovation is communicated through certain channels over time among the participants in a social system. The origins of the diffusion of innovations theory are varied and span multiple disciplines. The four main elements of diffusion are the innovation, communication channels, time, and the social system.

It is the perceived newness of the innovation, and the uncertainty associated with this newness, that is a distinctive aspect of innovation decision making (Rogers, 1995). This theory is relevant to this study owing to the fact that, it presents the process of newness, implementation and consequences of the innovation as regards the TSA policy.

2.3 Empirical Review

Arafa and Dickson (2022) analyses the effect of the treasury single account (TSA) on the financial performance of commercial banks in Tanzania over the period 2015-2020. The study employs a descriptive research design and the CAMEL Rating Analysis approach. The findings show that all the selected commercial banks have maintained a strong position on their composite rating system before and after the TSA implementation. They are sound in the aspects of capital adequacy, management quality, earning capacity and liquidity conditions.

Ogungbade, Oshatimi and Kolawole (2021) examined the effects of Treasury Single Accounts (TSA) on the revenue generation of federal government parastatals in Ekiti state. Both Descriptive and inferential statistics were used. The descriptive statistics include mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum while the study employed paired sample t-test for inferential analysis. The study reveals that TSA has not enhanced the revenue generation among federal government parastatals in Ekiti state. The research further shows that TSA is counterproductive since average revenue generated after the implementation of TSA is lower than the average revenue that the parastatals generated before the implementation of TSA.

Alisson and Ndukelwe (2021) examine the role of TSA. The paper adopted the content analysis as means of gathering and analysis of data. The paper observed that as envisaged, the implementation of TSA has enthroned centralized, transparent and accountable revenue management in Nigeria by instilling fiscal discipline and ensuring effective aggregate control over government cash balances.

Akpotu and Atagboro (2020) examined the implementation dynamics and its impact on TSA in Nigeria. The descriptive survey design was adopted and convenience sampling technique was employed in selecting 520 employees from finance and administration units in federal government ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs) in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used in the analysis of data. Based on the analysis, it was found that there are implementation dynamics that impact on TSA in Nigeria.

Ivungu, Ganyam, Alematu, Agbo and Ote (2020) examined the effect of treasury single account (TSA) on corruption in the Nigerian Public Sector. The extent to which TSA has affected the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) in Nigeria triggered this study. Data were obtained from Transparency International from 2012 to 2014 (before TSA adoption) and 2016-2018 (after TSA adoption), with 2015 as the base year. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and paired samples t-test statistics. The study findings revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean of corruption perception index (CPI) before and after TSA adoption in Nigeria.

Nwolisa, Ogochukwu, Madubuko and Ameachi (2020) investigated the effect of treasury single account (tsa) on Nigerian banks performance. Data was obtained from CBN Statistical Bulletin from 2011 to 2018. In testing the hypothesis, regression analysis was used with aid of E-view 9.0. The study concluded that the Federal Government Deposit has significantly improved on credit to the private sector after the implementation of TSA in Nigeria. On the bases of the finding, it was suggested that Central Bank should maintain a flexible monetary policy rate (MPR) at a minimum level in order to assist banks in taking alternative measures of meeting the emergency of cash withdrawal and lending demands of the customers.

Onodi, Eyisi and Akujor (2020) studied the effect of Treasury Single Account (TSA) implementation on the financial performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. The study employed expo-facto survey research design and seven big commercial banks in Nigeria. First Bank of Nigeria, Zenith Bank, Access Bank, UBA, Union Bank, Diamond Bank and Fidelity Bank were judgmentally sampled for this study. Secondary data were gathered through CBN statistical bulletin from 2013 to 2017. Customers deposit was used as proxy for independent variable (Treasury Single Account), while profit after tax, return on equity and return on assets is proxies for dependent variable (financial performance). The data collected were analyzed using comparable mean, while research hypotheses were tested using Simple regression analysis. The findings obtained from the statistical testing of the hypotheses of this study show that customers' deposit has a significant effect on profit after tax, return on assets and return on equity of commercial banks in Nigeria.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research study adopted the *ex post facto* research design. The choice of adopting the *ex post facto* research design is because the variables of interest are secondary in nature and verifiable. The study population of this study covered the 25 commercial banks in Nigeria as at 31st December, 2022.

Considering the fact that, the study variables are aggregate data, the study sampled all the 25 commercial banks as recorded by the CBN as at 31st December, 2022. Hence, the study adopted the census sampling technique. This sampling technique is appropriate considering the fact that, it is feasible for empirical investigation whose population and sample size equals.

The Time Series data used for the study was obtained from secondary sources such as the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The study covered data from the period 2001-2022. The data extracted include: Federal Government Deposits, Asset Quality Ratio-A.

The ordinary least square estimation technique was used to test the research hypotheses. The model was also subjected to various diagnostic tests such as Heteroskedasticity test, autocorrelation/serial correlation test, Ramsey RESET test for omitted variables and CUSUM test for stability. Accordingly, these tests were conducted through the instrumentality of Econometric Views version 9.0.

This study adopted Arafa and Dickson (2022) model but our model differs from their model as we incorporate sensitivity to market risk into our model. The modified model is stated as:

Model One:

$$CAR = \beta_0 + \beta_1TSA + \mu \text{-----} 1$$

Model Two:

$$ASR = \beta_0 + \beta_1TSA + \mu \text{-----} 1$$

Where:

- TSA = Treasury Single Account
- ASR = Asset Quality Ratio measured by non-performing loan ratio
- β_0 = Intercept
- β_1 = Coefficient

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Data Analysis

4.1.1. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were presented in this part of the study so as to assess the relationship between explanatory variable (TSA) and dependent variable (Performance).

Table 1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Observations
TSA	604.4167	292.7200	2931.600	28.34000	700.0402	22
CAR	14.80810	14.60000	18.56000	10.48000	2.118442	22
ASR	21.27952	14.80000	55.77000	2.960000	16.85206	22

Source: E-Views version 9.0 (2023)

Table 1 indicates that CAR has a mean value of 14.08% as against its minimum value of 10.48% and maximum value of 14.6%. The mean value implies that banks on the average meet up with the CBN minimum CAR requirements. The Central Bank of Nigeria requires national/regional banks to maintain a minimum of 10% CAR and 15% for international banks. The mean value of 14.08% for CAR is an indication that the Nigerian banks in Nigeria are moderately capitalized to withstand threat of solvency.

Similarly, the mean value for asset quality measured by non-performing loan ratio stood at 21.28% as against the minimum value of 2.96% and maximum value of 55.77%. The implication is that on the average 21.28% of the loans granted by deposit money banks during the period under investigation are non-performing, which may become impaired, bad and difficult to recover. The average value is above the regulatory limit of 5%. This shows that quoted deposit money banks did fairly bad when it comes to management of loans during the period under review. The minimum value for non-performing ratio is

relatively good suggesting that during a particular year a bank has only 1% of loans granted to customers as non-performing, and the maximum value of 55.77% is very high, disturbing and unacceptable. Poor credit analysis and unfavourable macro-economic environment may be responsible for these high non-performing loans.

4.13. Correlation Analysis

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

	Model 1		Model 2	
	CAR	TSA	ASR	TSA
CAR	1.000000	0.630814	ASR	1.000000
TSA	0.630814	1.000000	TSA	-0.482604
				1.000000

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

From the correlation results in Table 2, CAR with correlation coefficient values of 0.630814. This reveals that, CAR has positive yet moderate relationship with TSA. By implication, the more CAR, the higher the federal government deposits. However, ASR with correlation coefficient values of -0.482604. By implication, the higher the ASR, MAE, and SMR, the lower the volumes of federal government deposits and vice versa.

4.1.4. Diagnostic Tests

Table 3: Heteroskedasticity Test (HER)

Model	F-statistic	Prob. F(1,19)	Conclusion
One: CAR = $\beta_0 + \beta_1TSA + \mu$	0.061809	0.8063	Model 1 is Homoskedastic
Two: ASR = $\beta_0 + \beta_1TSA + \mu$	0.345197	0.5638	Model 2 is Homoskedastic

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity test result shows that the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity cannot be rejected at 1%, 5% or 10% level of significance

Table 4: Ramsey Reset Test (RRT)

Model	F-statistic	Df	Prob. F(1,19)	Conclusion
One: CAR = $\beta_0 + \beta_1TSA + \mu$	1.294701	(1, 19)	0.2701	Variable Well-specified
Two: ASR = $\beta_0 + \beta_1TSA + \mu$	0.441171	(1, 19)	0.5150	Variable Well-specified

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

As seen in Tables 4, the Ramsey Reset Test (RRT) showed that, the models are reliable, well-specified, and that the models are not faced with no variable perturbations. This further reveals that, the models are reliable and fit for policy formulations.

4.2. Test of Hypotheses

The decision rule for the hypothesis is to accept the alternative hypothesis if the p-value of the test statistic is less or equal than the alpha and to reject the alternative hypothesis if the p-value of the test statistic is greater than Alpha at 5% significance level. Each of the hypotheses are stated presented in table 5 to 6:

Tables 5: Test of Hypothesis One

Dependent Variable: CAR

Method: Least Squares

Date: 08/12/23 Time: 13:54

Sample: 2001 2022

Included observations: 22

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	13.65429	0.491375	27.78790	0.0000
TSA	0.435524	0.147778	2.947146	0.0090
R-squared	0.597927	Mean dependent var		14.80810
Adjusted R-squared	0.566239	S.D. dependent var		2.118442
F-statistic	12.55763	Durbin-Watson stat		1.575754
Prob(F-statistic)	0.002169			

Source: Eviews Version 9.0 (2023)

The R² of 0.597927 indicates that about 59.79% of total variation in the dependent variable (CAR) is accounted for by the explanatory variable (i.e. TSA). This result remains robust even after adjusting for

the degrees of freedom (d.f.) as indicated by the value of adjusted R^2 , which is 0.566239 (i.e. $\approx 56.62\%$). Thus, the regression has a good fit. The F-statistic, which is a test of explanatory power of the model is 12.55763 with the corresponding probability value of 0.002169, is statistically significant at 1%. Therefore, this implies that the explanatory variable (TSA) have joint significant effect on bank capital base. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.575754 indicates that the model is not prone to autocorrelation. Based on the regression result in table 5, TSA captured by federal government deposits (FGD) has a positive (coef= 0.435524) yet significant (p-value=0.0090<5% and t-value=2.947146>1.96) effect on bank capital adequacy ratio at 5% level of significance. Based on this, the null hypothesis one is rejected as expected.

Tables 6: Test of Hypothesis Two

Dependent Variable: ASR

Method: Least Squares

Date: 08/12/23 Time: 13:59

Sample: 2001 2022

Included observations: 22

Variable	Coefficien t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	28.30147	4.412142	6.414452	0.0000
TSA	-0.460583	0.216974	-2.122758	0.0488
R-squared	0.632907	Mean dependent var	21.27952	
Adjusted R-squared	0.592533	S.D. dependent var	16.85206	
F-statistic	5.768826	Durbin-Watson stat	1.638225	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.026703			

Source: Eviews Version 9.0 (2023)

The R^2 of 0.632907 indicates that about 59.79% of total variation in the dependent variable (ASR) is accounted for by the explanatory variable (i.e. TSA). This result remains robust even after adjusting for the degrees of freedom (d.f.) as indicated by the value of adjusted R^2 , which is 0.592533 (i.e. $\approx 59.92\%$). Thus, the regression has a good fit. The F-statistic, which is a test of explanatory power of the model is 5.768826 with the corresponding probability value of 0.026703, is statistically significant at 1%. Therefore, this implies that the explanatory variable (TSA) have joint significant effect on bank capital base. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.638225 indicates that the model is not prone to autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic, which is close 2.00, suggests that the model does not suffer from first order autocorrelation. Thus, the estimates of the model are reliable and should be taken with high degree of confidence. This was later emphasized by further diagnostics performed on the mode.

Based on the regression result in table 6, TSA captured by federal government deposits (FGD) has a negative (coef= -0.460583) yet significant (p-value=0.0488<5% and t-value=-2.122758>1.96) effect on asset quality at 5% level of significance. Based on this, the null hypothesis two is rejected as expected.

4.3 DISCUSSIONS OF RESULTS

Based on the regression result in table 5, TSA captured by federal government deposits (FGD) has a positive (coef= 0.435524) yet significant (p-value=0.0090<5% and t-value=2.947146>1.96) effect on bank capital adequacy ratio at 5% level of significance. Based on this, the null hypothesis one is rejected as expected. By implication, capital adequacy of DMBS in Nigeria was significantly sufficient and qualitative through the adoption of the TSA. This further revealed that, the implementation of TSA is highly instrumental to the higher capital base of the Nigerian banking industry. The findings show that all the commercial banks have maintained a strong position on their composite rating system as a result of the TSA implementation. Justifiably, they are sound in the aspects of capital adequacy. This result

supports the findings of Arafa, and Dickson (2022); Ndubuaku, Ohaegbu, and Nina (2017); Ekubiat and Ime (2016); Udo and Esara (2016) but deviated sharply from Oru and Odumusor (2019); Ofurum, Oyibo and Ahuche (2018); Saratu, Lenka, Levi and Titus (2017).

Based on the regression result in table 6, TSA captured by federal government deposits (FGD) has a negative (coef= -0.460583) yet significant (p-value=0.0488<5% and t-value=-2.122758>1.96) effect on asset quality at 5% level of significance. By implication, TSA has a counterproductive (depleting) effect on the quality of the asset base of the Nigerian banking industry. The possible traceable factor is the ever rising rate at which the loans which the deficit economic units collect in the Nigerian banking industry are not serviced regularly. This further suggests the need for policy makers in the Nigerian banking industry to ensure that, before loans are approved; proper check should be done otherwise the rising cases of non-performing loans would continue to deplete the quality of the asset base of the Nigerian banking industry.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the study concludes that the Treasury single accounts significantly improved on bank capital adequacy ratio but had a counterproductive effect on asset quality. In line with the findings and the conclusion reached in this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Nigerian bank regulators must as a matter of importance ensure that, the current capital adequacy ratio is sustained. Also, the apex banks must ensure that, banks whose capital adequacy ratio is below the minimum benchmark of 10 percent for banks with national presence should be sanctioned.
- ii. Bank management should ensure that, the rising cases of default should be addressed by ensuring that, proper character checks are conducted before loans are approved.

REFERENCES

- Adeagbo, K., & Oladeji, W. (2019). Treasury Single Account: a tool for preventing leakages and enhancing accountability of public funds in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Review*, 2(4), 69-83.
- Akpotu C. & Atagboro E. (2020) Implementation dynamics and impact of treasury single account (TSA) in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 8(1), 48-56.
- Alisson P. & Ndukwe O. J (2021). Towards achieving Public Accountability in Nigeria Public Sectors: The Role of Treasury Single Account (TSA). *International Journal of Academic Accounting, Finance & Management Research*, 5(1), 20-30.
- Arafa, S., & Dickson, P. (2022). Effect of treasury single account (TSA) on the financial performance of commercial banks in Tanzania: A study based on CAMEL rating analysis. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 11(2), 172–182
- Arafa, S., & Dickson, P. (2022). Effect of treasury single account (TSA) on the financial performance of commercial banks in Tanzania: A study based on CAMEL rating analysis. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 11(2), 172–182
- Ekubiat .E, Edet. N, (2016). An analysis of pros and cons treasury single account policy in Nigeria. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 5(4), 23-31.
- Ewiwile, S., Sinebe, M. T., Mokobia, N. A., Agbogun, O. E., & Ighoroje, J. (2024). Pre and Post Treasury Single Account (TSA) Implementation and the Nigeria's Macroeconomic Performance. *Journal of Ecohumanism*, 3(6), 1019-1033.
- Ivungu, J. A., Ganyam, A. I., Agbo, A., & Ola, P. O. (2020). Effect of treasury single account (TSA) on corruption in the Nigerian Public Sector. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(3), 43–53.
- Kanu, I. E. (2016). Adoption of treasury single account (TSA) by the Governments of Nigeria: Benefits, challenges and prospects, *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(3), 126-130.
- Ndubuaku, Y.O., Ohaegbu, A.G., & Nina, O.C. (2017). The impact of treasury single account on Ministries, Department, and Agencies (MDAs) accounting information and accountability: a

- conceptual review. Proceedings of the Academic Conference of Sub-Sahara Africa Academic Research Publications on New Direction and uncommon Changes 2(4), 1-14
- Nwolisa E. F, Ogochukwu V. O, Madubuko U. C & Ameach M.P. (2020) Effect Of Treasury Single Account (Tsa) on Nigerian Banks Performance. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research (Social and Management Sciences)*, 6(6), 1-10.
- Ofurum, C., Oyibo, P & Ahuche, Q. (2018). Impact of treasury single account on government revenue and economic growth in Nigeria: a pre – post design. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business & Social Science*, 8(4), 283-292.
- Ogungbade O, Oshatimi O. O and Kolawole A. D (2021) Treasury Single Account Policy and Revenue Generation Among Federal Parastatals in Ekiti-State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Financial Research*, 12(4), 1-20.
- Onodi B. E, Eyisi A. S & Akujor J. C. (2020). Treasury Single Account (TSA) Implementation and Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5(6), 20-30.
- Onuorah AC, & Chigbu EE (2016). F ederal government treasury single account (TSA) deposits and commercial banks performance. *Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 11(3), 1-13.
- Onuorah, A.C. Ehiedu, V.C. & Egugbo, R.U. (2023). CAMELS rating and its effects on FUGAZ banks' performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Xidian University*, 17(2), 248- 257.
- Uche, C. U. (2018). Banking regulation in the era of structural adjustment: The case of Nigeria. *Journal of financial Regulation and Compliance*, 8(2), 57-165
- Udo, U. A. & Esara, Y.K. (2016). Implementation of TSA and Nigerian economy. Business & Economy, Market Development, Report generated on Thu, 21 Apr 2016.
- Yusuf M (2016). Effects of treasury single account on public finance management in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7(6), 164-170.